

Mechanism of Iodination of Aminochromes

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The aminochromes obtained from the oxidation of catecholamines with iodine or with potassium iodate are iodinated, usually, at the C₇-position¹. It has been further observed that aminochromes having substituents at the C₇-position do not produce iodoaminochromes thus confirming that the C₇-position is the normal position for iodination. The iodoaminochromes are formed^{1,2} by a two stage process: (i) initial oxidation of the catecholamine entity to the aminochrome, (ii) followed by its iodination at the C₇-position to give the corresponding iodoaminochrome. While the mechanism of the first stage is well understood¹ that of the second is still obscure.

In this communication is envisioned the intermediacy of a 1 : 1-aminochrome-iodine charge-transfer complex, of the amine-halogen donor-acceptor type³, enroute to 7-iodoaminochromes. We have earlier shown^{4,5} from the visible and uv absorption spectra of dilute solutions of iodine and N, N-dimethylaniline (DMA) in methylenechloride, the existence of a similar complex system. The DMA-I₂ complex so formed, changed slowly in methylenechloride and rapidly in presence of water, into *p*-iododimethylaniline, and finally (through disproportionation³ of the latter) to crystalviolet cation. The mesomeric ion (Ib) of the aminochrome may be viewed as a DMA analogue and as such would undergo similar transformations by interaction with iodine.

Studies of the optical properties of mixtures of adrenochromes⁶ (ca. 1.5×10^{-3} M) in acetonitrile and iodine (ca. $0.8-2 \times 10^{-2}$ M) in the same solvent formed the basis of the proposed mechanism.

It was observed that the visible iodine absorption in acetonitrile at λ_{510} m μ was shifted to shorter wavelength, broad band at 450-84 m μ , upon adding adrenochrome solutions and that there was a fine isosbestic point. Further, the initially feeble triiodide band at 350-55 m μ increased in intensity with time and the broad band around 450 m μ was finally replaced by a peak at 528-30 m μ due to the formation of 7-iodo-adrenochrome. The results indicate that a 1 : 1 molecular complex of iodine and adrenochrome is formed in solution and that the complex is in equilibrium as is expressed by eqn. (1). The adrenochrome-iodine molecular complex (eqn. 1) rapidly changes from an 'outer complex' to

an 'inner complex' (eqn. 2). The passage of eqn. (2) to the right would liberate iodide ions

1. R. A. Heacock in 'Advances in Heterocyclic Chemistry', Ed. A. R. Katritzky, Academic Press, N. Y., vol 5, 1965, p. 287.
2. G. L. Matlock and D. L. Wilson, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1967, 45, 327.
3. C. Reid and R. S. Mulliken, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 76, 3869.
4. S. Ghosal and S. K. Dutta, *Ind. J. Chem.*, in press.
5. S. Ghosal and S. K. Dutta, this *Journal*, 1967, 44, 239.
6. Adrenochrome was prepared according to the method of Heacock *et al* (R. A. Heacock, C. Norenburg and A. N. Payza, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1958, 35, 853).

(eqn. 3) and the latter would form triiodide ions, as is evident from the increase in intensity of the peak at 350.55 μ , according to eqn. (4).

The above general equilibria (eqns. 1-4) is reasonable in view of the existence of similar equilibria in pyridine-iodine⁵ and in DMA-iodine⁴ systems.

Supporting evidence to the participation of the adrenochrome-I₂ 1 : 1 molecular complex in the nuclear iodination of adrenochrome was further gained through the observed formation of an aminochrome-zinc acetate molecular complex. The blue precipitate obtained from adrenochrome methylether with zinc acetate has all the properties of a 1 : 1 molecular complex⁷ having an additional zinc acetate substituent in the nucleus.

Finally, the analogy^{4,5} of formation of *p*-iododimethylaniline from DMA-I₂ molecular complex is extended here to account for the formation of 7-iodoadrenochrome (VI) from the 'inner complex' (II) via (III-VI). The oxidative transformation of aminochromes to mel-

nins⁸ would follow a similar sequence.

The stability of several 7-iodoaminochromes is currently being studied in this laboratory.

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7. Details of this study are being reported elsewhere. Cf. also, R. A. Heacock and G. L. Mattok, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1965, 41, 139.

8. R. I. T. Cromatic and J. Harley-Mason, *Biochem. J.*, 1957, 66, 713.